

T(s)	Mag						
1393206	0.75						
1597835	0.58						
3748799	0.57						
3903930	0.60						
3930968	0.76						
4049352	0.67						
4190656	0.62						
4211701	0.59						
6422344	0.58						
6518877	0.61						
6531292	0.58						
6598919	0.57						
6603521	0.63						
8532252	0.65						
9164064	0.71						
9212644	0.57						
9228356	0.63						
9310457	0.60						
9440113	0.57						
11516117	0.58						
11655658	0.59						
11783560	0.61						
14048654	0.64						
14104366	0.56						
14495298	0.57						
16676175	0.62						
16678981	0.61						
16673944	0.60						
16687419	0.58						
16828955	0.61						

Table B-2: 0-reduced time series of 210 earthquakes from Table B-1 that occurred during the Moon's traversals of the Earth's magnetotail, i.e., within three days from the full Moon.

T(s)	Mag						
15486568	0.60						
15532608	0.66						
57741	0.61						
334022	0.60						
614223	0.58						
717749	0.60						
910557	0.71						
1019740	0.61						
1105692	0.60						
1170437	0.57						
1923610	0.59						
1917040	0.61						
2141289	0.65						
2414137	0.68						
2426257	0.57						
2507932	0.57						
2533855	0.65						
2671659	0.64						
2739512	0.68						
2817613	0.58						
2989531	0.67						
3061455	0.57						
3167007	0.58						
3225189	0.59						
3276943	0.65						
3404098	0.70						
3629408	0.61						
4355804	0.59						
4522340	0.58						
4800528	0.71						
5007241	0.72						
5189145	0.68						
5198515	0.60						
5281749	0.57						
5914428	0.65						
6023688	0.60						
6085738	0.58						
6116980	0.60						
6886538	0.58						
7092054	0.58						
7146274	0.63						
7193189	0.58						
7241173	0.58						
7394954	0.67						
7493107	0.59						
7519089	0.60						
7563824	0.57						
7748155	0.56						
7960557	0.57						
8062920	0.65						
8054717	0.62						
8124545	0.59						
8161734	0.57						
8197195	0.58						
8274561	0.61						
8274568	0.66						
8302096	0.57						
8674100	0.59						
8842828	0.59						
9656944	0.72						
9794575	0.60						
9885879	0.62						
9955396	0.57						
10234881	0.64						
10343249	0.58						
10480989	0.60						
10597019	0.63						
10803978	0.62						
10941457	0.58						
11006000	0.57						
11061187	0.60						
11097118	0.59						
11199149	0.61						
11262597	0.60						
12141218	0.61						
12455622	0.78						
12574304	0.58						
12848021	0.60						
13386390	0.63						
13530574	0.57						
13883946	0.60						
13919425	0.60						
14634325	0.58						
14717930	0.56						
15010981	0.59						
15071330	0.61						
15108834	0.60						
15204468	0.69						
15375796	0.59						
15458327	0.57						
15458563	0.67						
15462091	0.60						

Table B-3: 0-reduced time series of 635 earthquakes from Table B-1 that occurred during the Moon's traversals of the interplanetary magnetic field, i.e., the events listed in Table B-1 but not in Table B-2.